

Make Data Count: Driving metrics for the meaningful evaluation of data

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Abstract

In order to successfully evaluate the impact and reach of data, there is a need for metrics that treat data as primary research outputs. Make Data Count is an initiative that works to develop metrics that allow the community to understand how data are used and how they advance research and policy. Make Data Count collaborates with groups across the research data ecosystem to create and implement workflows for recording information about how data sets are accessed and used; those measures provide the necessary foundation for further contextualization leading into meaningful data metrics. Spanning across disciplines, sectors, and geographies, Make Data Count fosters innovation in data evaluation. We develop standards to capture comparable and consistent counts of data citations, downloads and views, and scalable infrastructure to collect, aggregate and share usage measures, openly and through integration with workflows to index research information. We support projects that build the research evidence needed to identify metadata gaps and to benchmark data metrics to respond to the needs of diverse users. And importantly, we believe that data must be incorporated into research evaluation processes such as funding applications or tenure and promotion processes so that researchers are rewarded for the data they share and their impact. We invite the community to contribute to the development of meaningful data metrics so that, through collaboration, we can create a system where data are regularly assessed, evaluated, and rewarded.

Make Data Count is an initiative working to catalyze the development and adoption of open data metrics. As efforts toward data sharing have come to the fore, and more and more datasets are available, we have a responsibility to scrutinize whether and how data are being used, and whether they advance our goals to catalyze research progress and societal benefit. If we are to answer those questions, inform policy developments to maximize the value of data and create mechanisms to reward researchers for their data contributions, we need data metrics that will help us understand how data are accessed and used, as part of research and policy activities.

Make Data Count's vision is clear: data should be seen and treated as first-class research outputs. Like any research contribution, data deserve to be recognized, evaluated, and rewarded. For this vision to become a reality, the metrics we use must be auditable and meaningful—they need to represent the provenance and reach of data in a way that can be trusted, verified, and replicated. These metrics should be contextualized beyond simple counts and reflect the multifaceted ways in which data contribute to research progress.

Data metrics are an opportunity to look at measures of the usage and impact of research contributions from a new perspective. Traditional research outputs, like articles, have long been assessed using metrics such as publication numbers and citations, but data have their own unique role in the research process and are used in many ways that are often invisible or uncounted by conventional metrics. Make Data Count aims to bring those nuanced dimensions to light, recognizing that datasets are accessed, downloaded, reused, cited, and engaged with in ways that differ from other research outputs (1). We need metrics that can capture the full spectrum of these interactions, allowing us to see the value data provide as their own product, often unrelated to a traditional publication.

Make Data Count's work on data metrics started ten years ago through a collaboration between the California Digital Library, the Public Library of Science, and the Data Observation Network for Earth that led to a survey that collected insights into preferences for metrics of the impact of data (2). This research highlighted that researchers and data managers strongly favored data citations and downloads as measures of impact. Make Data Count used these results to inform its next projects, which focused on workflows to capture citations to data via repositories and journals, and the standardization of counts for data downloads and views (3), through partnerships with [DataCite](#) and [COUNTER](#). Recognizing that no single entity can develop a comprehensive data metrics system on its own, Make Data Count has drawn on expertise from diverse fields and institutions to co-create tools and standards. Over the years, we have worked closely with repositories to develop and implement recommended practices, and with bibliometricians to gain a broader understanding of data usage practices among researchers (4). We have pursued our partnership with DataCite to develop and deploy infrastructure to capture, store and share data usage information. Building on these foundations, our current activities and projects aim to scale the data usage information available to the community, and to bring additional context to usage measures so that they respond to the needs of diverse users. At the same time, we continue to

have a focus on fostering community engagement, and our activities are possible thanks to contributions by community members across institutions, publishers, and repositories, and collaborations with the National Science Foundation, Sloan Foundation, Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation, Wellcome Trust, Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, the [NIH-funded Generalist Repositories Ecosystem Initiative](#) and many others.

Make Data Count operates within a larger global effort to promote open data. From national mandates to institutional policies (5,6), the open data movement is growing, and we are embedded in that landscape. However, our focus is distinct: we are here to evaluate what happens **after** data are shared. While much of the conversation in research data revolves around making data FAIR (7), it is equally important to develop best practices for what happens once data are published—who is using the data, how they're using the data, and what impact they are having.

Data metrics

Make Data Count defines data metrics as meaningful, contextualized, quantitative or qualitative measures of how data sets are accessed or used (8). For data metrics to be meaningful, they must include three interwoven components: 1) quantitative measures of data usage, for example, in the form of data citations or counts of data views and data downloads; 2) qualitative measures such as narrative summaries of the impact of a particular dataset or the extent of collaborations enabled; and 3) contextual information, supported by the standards applied to report usage metrics and the metadata that enriches the information about the dataset and its usage. All three elements are necessary for data metrics to be meaningful, that is, to enable usage to be normalized across relevant axes (e.g. per discipline), comparable across platforms, and trusted.

Make Data Count has led pivotal work to enable the community to normalize, report, and access data citations, as well as data views and downloads (1). While our work so far has focused on these quantitative measures and the standards to normalize them, we recognize that these are just some of the pieces in a larger fabric of interactions with datasets that we should seek to capture. There are many types of data, and researchers increasingly interact with them in a variety of ways, many of which do not involve a download or a citation. We want to work with the community to develop frameworks, infrastructure, and standards that allow us to capture those interactions at scale, so that they can also be counted in future evaluation.

In our journey to develop responsible data metrics that the community can trust, we know that our work must be informed by evidence and founded on a principle of openness. Developing and applying evidence through empirical research into data usage behaviors, practices and trends is key in order to ensure that we continually evolve and respond to the community's needs. We have an opportunity to move from a monolithic approach to metrics to one that is more iterative, where metrics to understand how data feeds into research and policy are enriched, corrected or created to respond to evolving and new community uses. For data metrics to be trusted, they must also be supported by a principle of openness; the community must be able to understand and access the

quantitative, qualitative and contextual information that underlies the metrics, so that we can collectively scrutinize, audit and iterate on those metrics.

Make Data Count: A community hub to advance data metrics

To work toward our goals, Make Data Count functions as a community hub that fosters collaboration across disciplines, sectors, and geographies. Our aim is to collectively advance the development of data metrics—building the fundamental tools and infrastructure needed to accurately and transparently assess the value of research data. By working together, we are shaping the future of how open data are evaluated and integrated into the research ecosystem.

Our efforts are centered around four major action areas: **Standards, Infrastructure, Evidence, and Incentives**.

Standards: Ensuring Transparency and Consistency

The evaluation of data must be built on a foundation of standards that ensure transparency, comparability, and consistency in how data usage is measured. Without clear standards, data usage metrics could be fragmented or misleading, limiting their utility in research evaluation.

One of the core standards we adhere to is the [COUNTER Code of Practice for Research Data](#). Co-developed by Make Data Count and COUNTER, this standard ensures that data usage measures—such as views, downloads, and citations—are collected in a consistent manner across platforms. It provides transparency about how the data are gathered, allowing users to trust the metrics they see. This standardization is crucial for allowing comparisons across datasets and between platforms, ensuring that data usage counts are not just accurate but also meaningful when aggregated from different sources.

Through our partnership with DataCite, we developed frameworks to collect data citations through metadata, allowing these connections between datasets and other outputs to be consistently captured across repositories. DataCite, Crossref and others have also worked to build frameworks that enable aggregating citations between datasets and articles, for example, through the Scholix framework (9) and the Event Data service. This has made it possible to have a common store of data citations, but through our work with repositories and journals, we recognized that capturing citations through metadata only would provide a partial picture of the use of data in publications - as data are often mentioned without including an accompanying structured citation. Our [Data Citation Corpus](#) project aims to address this challenge by aggregating citations registered through metadata as well as data mentions identified through text mining. As part of this work, we are exploring the metadata and workflows necessary to aggregate and consistently display asserted links between datasets and articles, identified through different methodologies, and for datasets with different identifiers (DOIs and accession numbers).

Infrastructure: Building the Tools for Scalable Data Metrics

To move forward, we need scalable, efficient infrastructure that supports the collection, aggregation, and sharing of data-usage measures. Make Data Count is working on building these essential tools and workflows so that data usage information can be gathered at scale and integrated into existing research ecosystems. This is more than a technical challenge—it's about creating a pathway for research data to be evaluated on par with traditional research outputs.

To this aim, we've developed DataCite workflows that capture and report essential metrics such as citations, views, and downloads. These workflows are scalable and designed to feed into broader systems that track research outputs. We've created a [usage tracker](#) that helps capture more granular interactions with datasets—it includes tracking of downloads and views in various forms. By tracking these interactions, we can better understand how datasets are being engaged with beyond the traditional citation framework. These are important steps, but we acknowledge that further work remains to be done to capture data usage across the repository ecosystem, incorporating datasets with different identifiers, and interactions through platforms that do not involve a static dataset record.

For data citations, the Data Citation Corpus serves as a vital resource for gathering existing mentions of data in journal articles and preprints. Importantly, the Corpus combines, for the first time, citations for datasets with DOIs and accession numbers, and invites contributions by community groups that are collecting data citations so that those can be made openly available for the community. The use cases that the Corpus can enable rely on metadata that will allow different users to interrogate the citations in the Corpus according to different facets relevant to them, and thus, in addition to aggregating the dataset-article links, the work on the Corpus also involves looking at ways to address metadata gaps. While the long-term solution remains to advocate for broad adoption of data citation best practices across the publishing and research ecosystems (10–12), this corpus offers a way for our community to create a clearer picture of how datasets are referenced and used in subsequent research. We invite groups and organizations who are undertaking work to trace connections between datasets and associated papers, or to enrich metadata associated with datasets, to get in touch about contributing to the Data Citation Corpus.

A key aspect of our infrastructure is that all the information about data usage collected and reported via our tools is openly available to the community. Data citations and usage counts deposited with DataCite and the citations in the Data Citation Corpus are available under a CC0 license for the community to access and reuse. This aligns with recent initiatives calling for openness in research information, such as the commitments set out in the [Barcelona Declaration on open research information](#).

Our infrastructure also extends to integrating with the broader ecosystem of research information. Service providers such as OpenAlex, Dimensions, and OpenAIRE aggregate and distribute data usage information collected from DataCite via Make Data Count infrastructure.

These partnerships allow for a more holistic view of data impact and help ensure that data metrics are visible and useful across the research community.

Through collaboration, infrastructure development, and adherence to standards, we are setting the stage for a future where data metrics are not just collected, but actively inform research practices, funding decisions, and policy-making.

Evidence: Understanding How Data Drives Research

If we are to meaningfully inform open-data policies, we need to hold ourselves accountable toward auditing whether and how data drive the research and societal benefits we hope to achieve. To this end, our work on data metrics must be done in tandem with research on data-usage practices. Evidence from qualitative research will provide insights on the motivations and perceived benefits and challenges that different actors see in data reuse. Qualitative studies can also surface new interactions with datasets that are not captured by current counts of data usage, and thus, inform and expand the range of data metrics that we develop. Bibliometric studies can provide large-scale insights into ongoing practices, diving deeper into the context relevant for different data users (e.g. across roles, geographical locations or disciplines) (13), and importantly, identify gaps in the metadata currently available that need to be tackled to enable further understanding into data use and reuse in different communities. This type of evidence is critical to inform what our next priorities should be regarding metadata for data usage measures. As an example, our collaboration with the Meaningful Data Counts project by the Scholcomm Lab highlighted a scarcity of discipline-level information for data citations (14), and as a result of this exploration, the Scholcomm Lab and DataCite have taken steps to improve the coverage of discipline information for data citations in DataCite metadata and in the Data Citation Corpus (15,16).

Research in recent years has focused on data citation practices, and has provided useful evidence in that area. Looking ahead, it will be important to undertake research to expand our conceptualization of what we mean by citation in the context of datasets, to look into usage patterns other than citations. It will also be important to understand interactions with data beyond static individual data records. Researchers are increasingly collecting and using dynamic data or datasets stored in federated hubs where they pick and combine data according to their specific needs. The development of machine learning models involves training on large groups of datasets. Research into these growing practices is needed to inform the standards and tools necessary to accurately capture and report this type of use.

We recognize that the infrastructure for tracking and reporting data citation and usage is still being adopted by the scholarly communications community. Bearing this in mind, we must understand what information is available and what is still missing, in order to define what data metrics are mature enough for their use in evaluation, and which ones require further enrichment and benchmarking for a meaningful application. Developing this evidence should be an iterative process where new practices of data usage and additional metadata are regularly researched, and

those research results used to inform the development of infrastructure and guidelines around data usage and how that information is collected and shared.

Incentives: Driving a Culture of Data Publishing and Data Reuse

Evaluation processes across academia and research are mainly focused on journal publications, often leaving aside data and other outputs (17). Make Data Count believes that the evaluation of the reach and impact of data must become a key element in research evaluation, for both individual researchers and research programs. This involves for example, incorporating data as a contribution to be listed on its own merit in tenure and promotion reviews and job or grant applications. To this end, suitable metrics for evaluating data must be used, and individuals with the skills necessary to complete an evaluation of data contributions must be included in such evaluation processes (18).

Data metrics need to be anchored on comprehensive and standardized information, and at this stage of adoption, it's too soon to declare that we can implement credit systems that fairly recognize and reward all uses of data. This is exactly why we advocate for a thoughtful approach, one that accounts for diverse disciplinary behaviors and researchers' and evaluators' needs. We recognize that transforming research evaluation processes to incorporate data will require multi-stakeholder input. We are engaging with diverse communities and groups to advance change so that research assessment incorporates data evaluation. We welcome the work that is already in progress by the Higher Education Leadership Initiative for Open Scholarship ([HELIOS Open](#)) and the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment ([CoARA](#)), which seek to advance reform of research assessment processes. Make Data Count has collaborated with different community groups to drive forward conversations about data metrics and research evaluation, for example, via the Research Data Alliance ([RDA](#)) and [FORCE11](#). More recently, we convened institutions, funders, policy makers, researchers, and infrastructure providers at the Make Data Count Summit, a dedicated forum to identify and tackle priorities to advance responsible data metrics and data usage evaluation (19). We will continue to catalyze these conversations and contribute to ongoing efforts to ensure data is part of the evaluation processes of the future.

Building a future where data are regularly evaluated and rewarded

Much remains to be done, and we're not sitting still. The work that Make Data Count has led over the last ten years provides a strong foundation to build on, and we are actively looking for ways to leapfrog some of the current challenges. By balancing careful development with bold action, we can ensure that when the time comes, the system we've built is both credible and impactful.

Importantly, community and collaboration remain our unwavering focus. Make Data Count exists to bring communities together as we work through the different pieces of technical and social scaffolding necessary to get to a place where data is regularly evaluated and valued as a primary research output.

Independent of individual roles or expertise, we can all contribute to treating and recognizing data as primary research outputs. Here are ways in which you can take part:

<p>Does your repository or platform collect data usage measures?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Implement one of the Make Data Count tools to standardize the counts, such as the usage tracker ✓ Share the usage counts with DataCite for aggregation and sharing with the community ✓ If you are collecting data citations, contact us about contributing to the Data Citation Corpus ✓ If you are collecting additional metadata for datasets or for data-article connections, reach out about contributing this to the existing pool of data usage information ✓ Explore the Data Citation Corpus data file (15) as a potential source of citations for data in your repository
<p>Do you complete evaluations of research outputs, or are interested in researching data-citation practices?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Explore the Data Citation Corpus data file (15) and use it as a source for your analyses or your research ✓ Share your feedback with us, let us know what gaps you identify vs. the analyses you planned to undertake ✓ Get in touch about your research project to explore a collaboration
<p>Do you have examples of how you evaluate the usage of data from your institution? Are you working on a project looking at data-usage practices?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Contact us so that we can amplify your story ✓ Get in touch to discuss possible collaborations
<p>Are you collecting information about data usage as part of your organization's processes? Are you looking to evaluate the reach of data from your programs?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Get in touch contributing those via Make Data Count workflows ✓ Explore the Data Citation Corpus data file (15) as a source of data citations for your evaluation

At its core, Make Data Count is about collaboration, collective advancement, and redefining what it means to share data. We advocate for ensuring that the focus on data goes beyond sharing to one where the use and reuse of data receives as much attention. Understanding the reach of data is key if we are to develop ways to reward the researchers who are contributing those datasets,

and ensure that data policies are fostering the behaviors and practices that will allow data to catalyze research and societal benefit. We believe that by working together to develop data metrics, we can create a system where data are regularly assessed, evaluated, and rewarded, and where due attention is given to data as the centerpiece of the research process.

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